

A Study of Consumer Buying Behaviour at Hyper Stores

Sagar F. Jadhav¹ and Aarti Deshpande²

¹Sr. Assistant Professor and ²Officiating Principal,

G. H. Rasoni College of Commerce, Science, Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India.

CITATION: Jadhav, Sagar F. and Deshpande, Aarti (2020), "A Study of Consumer Buying Behaviour at Hyper Stores", *MERC Global's International Journal of Management*, Vol. 8, Issue 2, pp. 53-56.

ARTICLE HISTORY: Submitted: February 08, 2020, Revision received: March 10, 2020, Accepted: March 20, 2020

ARTICLE TYPE: Research paper

ABSTRACT

Consumers are influenced by different tastes and preferences in the market from time to time. There have been several factors responsible for the changing market scenario such as social, cultural, psychological, and behavioural situations. The changing consumer taste and preferences, which has brought a massive change in today's market scenario. Today, it has been seen a new era in the market by opening up Hyper Stores. The prime aim of the research study was to analyse consumer buying behaviour at Hyper Stores in Nagpur city. The primary data was collected through the method of circulating surveys, interviews, and observation and secondary data were taken from books, research papers, reports, magazines, websites, and newspapers. A simple random sampling technique was adopted for the data collection. 200 respondents were taken for the research.

KEYWORDS: Consumer, Behaviour, Preferences, Big Bazaar, Nagpur City.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Akin, M. (1998), "Purchasing behaviour models of today's consumer", *Marketing World*, Vol. 12, Issue 68, pp. 24-35.
2. Barach, Jeffrey A. (1971), "Consumer Decision making and Self-confidence", *Indian Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 2, No. 3, pp. 18.
3. Chunawalla, S. A. (2000), *Commentary on Consumer Behaviour*, Himalaya Publishing House, New Delhi.
4. Day, R. R. (1977), *Extending the concept of consumer satisfaction*, Association for Consumer Research, Chicago.
5. Hansen, T. (2005), "Perspectives on Consumer Decision Making: an Integrated Approach", *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, Vol. 4, Issue 6, pp. 420-437.
6. Harry, Davis L. (1970), "Dimensions of Marital Roles in Consumer Decision Making", *Journal of Marketing Research*, Vol. VII, No. 2, pp. 168-177.
7. Kotler, P. and Armstrong, G. (1996), *Principles of Marketing*, Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs.
8. Kumar, Atul and Brar, Vinaydeep (2016), *Retailing Strategy: Products & Customer Services Perspective*, LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing, Germany.
9. Kumar, Atul; Joshi, Jena and Brar, Vinaydeep (2019), "Impact of Sales Promotion on Customer Purchase Intention With Respect to Organized Retail Industry", *International Journal for Research in Engineering Application & Management*, Vol. 05, Issue 02, May, pp. 905-913
10. Solomon, M. R. (1996), *Consumer behaviour buying, having and being*, Prentice-Hall International Editions, New Jersey.
11. Solomon, M.; Bamossy, G. and Askegaard, S. (1999), *Consumer behaviour: A European perspective*, Prentice Hall Europe.
12. Subadra, S.; Murugesan, K. M. and Ganapathi, R. (2010), "Consumer Perceptions & behaviour: A study with special reference to car owners in Namakkal District", *APJRB*, Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 37-57.
13. Wani, Navreen Tariq and Wani, Samreen Tariq (2011), "A Study of Comparative customer satisfaction with special reference to Retail outlets of Big Bazaar and Reliance Mart in Pune city", *PMR*, Vol. 10, Issue 2, pp. 47-55.